

A P O L L O

D7.2: Dissemination, communication and marketing plan

WP7 – Exploitation and Communication

*Authors: Nefeli Vasiliki Politi-Stergiou (Evenflow), Dimitrios PAPADAKIS (Evenflow),
Eleftherios MAMAIS (Evenflow), Igor Milosavljevic (Evenflow).*

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Lead Author	Nefeli Politi Stergiou	Email	nefeli@evenflowconsulting.eu	
	Evenflow	Phone	+32 494 44 8107	
Other authors	Dimitrios PAPADAKIS (Evenflow), Igor Milosavljevic (Evenflow), Eleftherios MAMAIS (Evenflow)			
Reviewer(s)	Polimachi SIMEONIDOU (DRAXIS), Dimitra PERPERIDOU (DRAXIS)			
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Executive summary

This report (D7.2) comprises the APOLLO updated Dissemination, communication and marketing plan, a comprehensive and living document which outlines the actions, tools and channels to be used throughout the project in the promotion of the services under development. The purpose of the document is to outline the strategy, activities, and tools with which the APOLLO project will communicate with a range of external stakeholders, as well as the timing of the various actions throughout the lifetime of the project. Further considerations and adjustments based on business plan aspects, communication messages and objectives are updated and described herein. The four Ps of marketing are presented as well as an updated marketing methodology based on the impact of D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I activities and the advancements of various business aspects presented in D7.10 Business Plan.

As assessed from these deliverables and D7.7/8 Dissemination Report I/II, regional communications are key for effective promotion. All APOLLO project partners have a role to play in WP7, especially the pilot partners in ensuring that effective communication is carried out in their regions through the allocated local contact points.

The primary target audiences for the APOLLO services are identified to be (small) farmers, agricultural consultants and farmer's cooperatives. In addition, research and academic communities, local and regional public authorities as well as the general public relevant targets for the communication effort. The media is an important target audience as it acts as a multiplier for APOLLO's promotion and users' engagement. Although smallholder farmers remain the primary target of the action, APOLLO also addresses to farmers with holdings of other sizes.

APOLLO makes use of a suite of tools, channels and activities to achieve its objectives, underpinned by an integrated and coherent visual identity which formed the basis for a commercial brand. In this phase the project is moving steadily to its commercial identity.

As an Innovation Action, APOLLO moves from being a project to a commercial service, and the communication, dissemination and marketing activities reflect this. This document shows the continuity in the shift from project-based to commercial activities. It presents the brand identity developed which is based on the project's visual identity as well as the new commercial name reflecting APOLLO's scope. In line with the brand identity the APOLLO website will be shortly updated with a commercial mini site before launching the final commercial site at a web address corresponding to the new name of the service, timed to coincide with the release of APOLLO's two new services and first platform working prototype. The updated plan highlights the marketing strategy, its principles and the foreseen activities. Communication and dissemination efforts will, from now onwards, to focus in amplifying and consolidating the marketing plan. Both actions will continue until the end of the project and are adjusted to engage the target audiences and serve APOLLO's promotional objectives, as updated since D7.1.

First pilot results are expected to be available in M28 and this will most likely be a milestone for the promotional activities. The communication and marketing plan takes into account the agricultural periods for each crop in the pilots and the milestones they imply to maximise promotional activities.

The impact of the APOLLO communication activities is being monitored on an ongoing basis and reported in the relevant deliverables (D7.7-9), using a set of Key Performance Indicators which were defined in D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I.

1 Introduction

This deliverable comprises the updated Dissemination, Communication and Marketing plan of the APOLLO project. The purpose of the document is to outline the strategy, activities, and tools with which the APOLLO project will communicate with a range of external stakeholders throughout the end of the project. This document will be updated during the project, with the final strategy to be described in M34, D7.11 Business Plan II.

As an Innovation Action APOLLO is expected to lead to “new products or services on the market” and “significant turnover for participants and the creation of a significant number of new jobs”. To this end the exploitation team has developed a strategy to achieve high quality project communication and dissemination activities and efficiently promote the APOLLO product.

APOLLO's WP7 addresses two primary objectives:

- 1. Fostering a sustainable customer base for the commercial service;**
- 2. Communicating the results and benefits of the project to relevant target audiences.**

Marketing addresses Objective 1, namely identifying and engaging with potential future customers of the APOLLO services. **Dissemination** will address the scientific, research and academic community, whereas **communication** focuses on the other audiences - both in support of Objective 2¹. These activities, although inter-related, have different audiences and different aims, which will be highlighted throughout the chapters which follow:

- Chapter 2 outlines the overall **strategy**;
- Chapter 3 describes the **core principles** governing all dissemination, communication and marketing activities;
- Chapter 4 presents the **dissemination** methodology and impact
- Chapter 5 presents the **communication** methodology and impact;
- Chapter 6 presents the **marketing** methodology and impact;
- Chapter 7 focuses on the **schedule and timing** of the various activities;
- Chapter 8 describes the means of **monitoring and evaluating** the impact of the activities.

¹ The term “communication will also be used in a general sense to refer to the whole package of activities in WP7.

2 Strategy

The strategy was first drafted in the previous deliverable *D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I* and a refined version was presented in *D7.10 Business Plan I*. In this document the overall strategy is presented with small adjustments as the overall business plan has not changed since the last document.

The approach to communication is tailored to take advantage of their specificities for maximum effect; selected messages must be delivered using the correct means, and the timing of communication activities should be designed for maximum impact.

Underpinning these concerns is a more fundamental issue concerning the **identity** of the action. APOLLO needs to move from being a project to a commercial service, and the communication, dissemination and marketing activities should reflect this. Branding is developed to achieve this goal, see section 3.4

A second underlying topic concerns the question of **partnerships**. This inevitably ties together with the work to be undertaken under the exploitation task of WP7, but it has been also examined in the context of its impact on the communication activities. The commercial services of APOLLO could gain a great deal from being offered as part of a partnership with an existing commercial provider of similar or complementary services. The options need to be identified and fully fleshed out before a coherent strategy can be constructed around them, but this issue remains strategically important for the success of the communication strategy as a whole.

A third major strategic issue is **regionalisation**. The APOLLO project is geared towards targeting three pilot countries, and promotional and communication materials are translated in to the three languages (Greek, Serbian and Spanish) by project partners, and customised in each case by the partners to highlight the specific benefits to farmers in the respective countries. The pilot partners have a direct role in acquiring local 'intelligence' in order to inform the most effective strategies for communication and marketing. Section 6.2 demonstrates the impact of these efforts thus far and the how APOLLO expects to further exploit the forthcoming feedback in regard to promotion.

All activities taken by the partners are reported in a series of documents: Dissemination Reports. The last Dissemination Report is due for M34 the last month of the lifetime of the project.

2.1 Approach

Five groups of activities underpin the approach to communication, marketing and dissemination activities, which are linked to basic questions which must be answered in the course of the project. The table below summarises the activities and questions.

Activity group	Questions
Identification	Who are we trying to reach, and why?
Content	What are the main messages to be delivered?
Methods	How will we get our messages across? Which tools should be used for which audiences?
Timing	When should communication actions take place?
Evaluation/Impact	What was the impact of the communication activities?

Table 1: Activity groups and key questions

The methodological approach to the dissemination, communication and marketing activities considers three cumulative levels of activity, which incrementally increase both the proximity to the audience and the depth of information:

Category	Purpose
INFORM	Raise a basic level of awareness of the APOLLO product, the project's goals, team and activities, and convey a general understanding of the purpose and benefits of the action. The goal here to use information activities as promotional means to engage interested parties.
ENLIGHTEN	Answer in detail key questions about the project's activities, its methodologies, the timing of its milestone and its results.
ENGAGE	In this phase engagement will mainly have promotional purpose. Involve the audience in the project's activities and maintain interest over the course of the project (and beyond). Moreover, from a commercial perspective, engagement entails the development of a customer-supplier relationship and is usually termed customer retention. Based on the methods used previously, more project focused, engagement continues through simple steps such as subscription to the project's newsletter, fully-fledged person-to-person interaction such as inviting participation in workshops, focus groups or other project events.

Table 2: Levels of communication activity

Each communication action is aimed at reaching one or more of the above levels across the different audiences (identified in Chapter 4), through the tools, channels and activities detailed in Chapter 6. Dissemination and Communication activities are aimed mainly at Informing and Enlightening the target audiences, whilst Marketing has the end goal of Engaging audiences.

2.2 Promotion by project partners

All APOLLO project partners are promoting the project using the means and channels at their disposal. Each partner promotes through their own channels the project amongst their stakeholder network and utilise their social media accounts to amplify (by means of "liking", "sharing" or "re-tweeting") the material published by the APOLLO accounts.

After the first results are available, the project partners from the pilot countries will be required to assist develop specific marketing plan for their region, drawing on their existing knowledge of the local specificities, stakeholder groups and communication channels. The plans will be presented to the final Dissemination Report (D7.9, M34).

Across all dissemination, communication and marketing activities APOLLO continues and will continue to follow until the end of the lifetime of the project, the project's principles, which were described in detail in the previous document of this series *D7.1 Dissemination, Communication and Marketing Plan I*.

2.3 Team organisation

The APOLLO Communication activities are led by the Communication Manager, Dimitrios Papadakis (EVF). However, **all APOLLO project partners have a role to play in WP7**. As described in section 3.1.1, pilot partners in particular will play a very important role in ensuring that effective communication is carried out in their regions, by (a) translating the communication and marketing materials produced by the WP7 leader (b) tailoring and regionalising the messages to apply to their local context and (c) serving as a local media contact point, both for outgoing communications and fielding incoming queries from potential customers or interested stakeholders.

For this reason, the following team organisation has been established, identifying local contact points in each pilot region for the translation and media activities:

Role	Translations	Media Relations
Greece	DRAXIS	Machi SIMEONIDOU (DRAXIS) msimeonidou@draxis.gr
Serbia	UBFCE, UPOR and external office	Dragutin PROTIC (UBFCE) drale74@yahoo.com

		Ugljesa TRKULJA (UPOR) ugljiesatrkulja@yahoo.com
Spain	AgriSat Maria DOLORES UBIDE mariadolores.ubide@agrisat.es	

Table 3: Contact points for communication tasks

3 Core Principles

A set of strategic principles underpinning the dissemination, communication and marketing effort have been identified which cut across and underpin the methodology for the activities in this work package:

- **Focus on the service, not the project.** Since the end-goal of APOLLO is a commercial service, the content of communication activities should increasingly reflect this shift, with a distinct marker placed between project-level communication (e.g. the use of terminology such as work packages, consortium, etc.) and service-level communication. This will most strongly be felt in the **change of name** and the establishment of a **commercial website**;
- **Establish a brand identity.** APOLLO needs to become widely recognisable as a brand with as much recognition and awareness as possible throughout the three years of the project. For this reason, the visual identity has been designed for continuity between the project phase and the subsequent commercial phase. In other words, even if the name “APOLLO” is changed to better reflect the content of the services, the visual elements will ensure that brand recognition is retained;
- **Focus on practical demonstration as a sales tactic.** The concept here is to directly present users with a sample of the APOLLO services (“showing” rather than “telling”), for example, through **screenshots of mocked-up information screens** in the brochure, factsheets and leaflets, through use case articles, etc;
- **Identify APOLLO champions amongst pilot users and early adopters.** The benefits of the service will be highlighted using quotes and stories from the pilots and early service users, directly demonstrating the value of the service rather than merely making claims about it;
- **Leverage multipliers and networks to maximise impacts.** Networks, associations and other groupings offer an opportunity for amplifying communication efforts with relatively little effort;
- **Highlight the whole chain of private and public economic and environmental benefits.** APOLLO emphasises the full range of its social, economic and environmental impacts, starting from the farmer (e.g who saves money on water and gains productivity) to the local economy (which benefits from improved competitiveness) to the general public (who benefit from reduced environmental degradation, better use of water resources, etc.).

3.1 Target Audiences

Target audiences are defined as all groups of people with common communication properties that APOLLO aims to target its dissemination, communication and marketing activities. The primary target audiences for the APOLLO services are APOLLO’s various customer groups: farmers, agricultural cooperatives, and agricultural consultants. The platform has additional features for the

latter two groups, allowing them to access the accounts of their customers or members. During the early stages of the APOLLO project, the strategic decision was taken not to limit the audience to smallholder farmers only – although these remain the primary target of the action, but to extend the offering to farmers with holdings of other sizes.

In addition, research and academic communities, local and regional public authorities as well as the general public and the media are relevant targets for the communication and dissemination effort.

For the marketing activities it is valuable to distinguish between two main groups, “customers” and “users”. The term “customer” refers to each party who is interested to buy the APOLLO services, while “user” is used for he/she who intends to use the services. A user is not necessarily a customer and vice versa. For example, if a cooperative buys the APOLLO services, the customer is the cooperative and the user is the group of farmers actually using the services.

The identified targets can be grouped into four categories:

Category	Description
Direct and intermediate customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Agricultural cooperatives and associations • Agricultural consultants • Food production companies • Agri-input providers
Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers • Agricultural cooperatives and associations • Agricultural consultants
Communication nodes and multipliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networks e.g. EUROGI, NEREUS, ENRD² • Associations e.g. COPA (Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations), COGECA (General Committee for Agricultural Cooperation in the European Union) • EU-level initiatives e.g. EIP-Agri
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialised (trade) media (Farmer’s Weekly); • General-purpose media.
Research and academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural universities and research centres.
Other relevant stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU-level actors (REA, DG ENTR, DG AGRI); • Local and Regional Authorities; • General public.

Table 4: Target audience categories

Each of these audiences is associated with specific communications, marketing or dissemination objectives, which are summarised in the table below (primary objectives are indicated in bold). Following the levels of activity described in the subchapter on approach (3.1.1), the right-most columns indicate whether the audience should be informed (INF), enlightened (ENL) or engaged (ENG).

Audience	Objectives	Activity
Farmers (primarily smallholders)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convince of the direct economic benefits of the service; • Generate direct customer leads; • Generate momentum for lobbying associations for bulk purchases; 	ENG
Agricultural Consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convince of the direct economic benefits of the service • Connect with the needs of users • Generate direct customer leads 	ENG

² European Network for Regional Development.

Agricultural Cooperatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convince of economic benefits to members • Generate potential customer leads through indirect propagation or direct lead through partnerships or joint supply arrangements 	ENG
Food production companies / Agri – input providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convince of benefits for partnership and selling opportunities 	ENG
Policy-makers / National, Regional and Local Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain visibility at institutional level; • Convince of value for national extension services; • Obtain support for relevant policies and measures. 	ENL
Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convince of economic benefits to sector and broader social/environmental benefits • Generate interest and potential indirect lead 	ENG
Specialised Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate interest in generating publications based on project success stories 	ENL
General Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate interest in communicating the socio-economic and environmental benefits of the project 	INF
Research and academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform of scientific progress and innovation developed during the project 	ENL
Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote socio-economic and environmental benefits and more broadly the beneficial outputs of EU-funded initiatives 	INF

Table 5: Audiences and primary objectives

Within the primary target audiences of farmers and agricultural consultants, it is envisaged that sub user groups can be identified based on:

1. Farm size: small holders or larger holdings
2. Farming methods: such as traditional or tech-savvy (can include organic farmers)
3. Crop type: each of all the crops that participated in the pilots.

More sub user groups can be generated by combining all the three features. However, the communication and marketing strategy will remain the same as it is based on the objectives focused on this basic distinction.

So far, two primary user groups are under validation in practice through the pilots:

- Traditionalist farmers/consultants, wary or critical of innovative technologies, and unwilling to risk costly investment in testing them;
- Technologically-savvy farmers or consultants, fully convinced of the potential of new innovative technologies to improve their professional lives.

The strategy for marketing to these two groups is distinct and relies on a combination of appropriate techniques; For accessing the second group, social media channels and tailored messages are mostly used. While access to more traditional groups is performed mostly through peer to peer presentations and traditional media.

3.2 Key messages

In responding to the question “what are the main messages to be delivered?”, a narrative framework is followed and identifies the key messages to be conveyed. In order for the messages delivered by the various communication, dissemination and marketing activities to be effective, coherent and mutually reinforcing, a narrative framework is required which binds them together and gives them context.

Based on the preliminary, working narrative framework for the APOLLO project an updated version is outlined as follows. This will be further elaborated as the project proceeds to encompass findings

such as those emanating from the first results from pilot users (WP6). Main messages in the second column are indicated in bold.

Following *D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I* and *D7.10 Business Plan I* a comprehensive description of the narrative and the key messages to be delivered to the different APOLLO target groups was presented. As the project has further evolved since the submission of the latest D7.10, key messages have been adjusted according to the project's advancements as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** All messages delivered will use simple, easy to understand language, while highly technical terms will be minimised.

Narrative element	Key Messages
<p>Context What is APOLLO?</p>	<p>APOLLO is an EU-funded project aiming to develop information services for small farmers in particular, as well as for farmer's associations and agricultural consultants.</p> <p>European funding is stimulating the development of innovative new services benefitting European farmers.</p> <p>APOLLO is a European undertaking built on European public investments.</p> <p><APOLLO commercial name> is a modular platform that provides agricultural services in order to support farmers take more informed decisions along the agricultural season.</p>
<p>Challenge What is the problem to be addressed by APOLLO services?</p>	<p>Farmers - especially smallholders - need to have high quality and increase productivity whilst remaining competitive and environmentally friendly.</p> <p>Improve resource management on the farm to improve final income.</p> <p>Farmers need to keep up with environmental standards and legislation.</p> <p>Smallholder farmers in particular struggle to access expensive, complicated high-tech solutions.</p> <p>Extreme weather events and/or rapid weather changes which can be tackled, can result in major damages for crops</p>
<p>Solution How do APOLLO services come to the rescue?</p>	<p>Users can take better more informed decisions, save time, energy and resources whilst achieving high quality and increasing productivity.</p> <p>Users can find the best time to till, reducing soil damage and using less energy.</p> <p>Users find the best time to irrigate, saving precious water.</p> <p>Users can keep an eye on crop health and alert the farmer to trouble spots.</p> <p>Users are facilitated to treat parts of a field differently according to their needs, saving fertiliser and pesticide.</p> <p>Users can estimate the size of the harvest and allow income calculation.</p> <p>Users get highly localised weather and temperature forecasts across each farm and improve proactiveness and/or reaction activities</p> <p>Users can provide precision agriculture advice on management zones, facilitating the organisation of labour and improving resource management and yield production</p> <p>Users are alerted for critical events for each service and for extreme and rapidly changing weather conditions</p>
<p>Differentiators What makes APOLLO special?</p>	<p>APOLLO services are based on accurate data, they are modular, affordable to all farmer groups, easy to use and accessible everywhere.</p> <p>Free European Union satellite data and automated processing make APOLLO services affordable.</p> <p>Any time or place, for many crops on multiple devices - APOLLO services are readily accessible.</p> <p>Built for farmers, by farmers: APOLLO follows a co creation process to make user valuable, user-friendly and easy to navigate services.</p>

	APOLLO is modular. It can be provided and can be easily customised according to the user's needs across all its target groups.
Impacts What effects will APOLLO have?	APOLLO services will enable farmers keep high standard yields, make their farms sustainable, more productive and competitive, whilst benefitting the environment.
	EU agriculture market will open up to all farmers by making information services available also to small farmers.
	Improve the competitiveness of EU farmers
	Customers and users will improve their competitiveness
	Environmental impact of agricultural activities can be reduced
Call to action What can you (the audience) do?	If you are a farmer, a representative of a farmers' association or cooperative, or an agricultural consultant - sign up to become a trial user of APOLLO services.
	If you would like to stay updated about the project and the commercial service - sign up to our newsletter and follow us on social media.
	If you think we share common goals meet us in <events APOLLO representatives will participate in> or/and contact us through our email and social platforms.

Table 6: Key messages

Key messages are being tailored when necessary according to the outcomes of the marketing strategy follow up and the business plan advancements. Results will serve as inputs for the development and delivery of the strong marketing campaign.

The framework presented in section 4.1 and the accompanying messages can be flexibly utilised in communication activities (all messages) or in the dissemination of results (chiefly **Context** and **Challenge**) and in marketing activities (from **Challenge** onwards). The trio of characteristics under **Differentiators** has been assessed and re defined ("modular, easy to use and co-created for the users with the users") and serves as a synthetic, multi-purpose tagline which can be replicated across multiple media and communication tools.

3.3 Main channels/tools

Channel selection and exploitation is fine-tuned as the project progresses. Regionalisation of tools and activities is identified to play key role in APOLLO's promotion. Thus, the most important aspect is tailoring the strategy based on the region. In this context, pilot activities play an important role in APOLLO progress and will act as key strategic points in the project's marketing plan. It is important to identify and understand which the profitable strategy for each pilot region would be. To achieve this, pilot partners are continuously assessing the reports coming from the co-creation process and the pilot phase. First outputs were presented in *D6.5 1ST Intermediate Evaluation Report*. More insights are expected in the next months with the milestone being the first pilot results in M28. The pilots together with the exploitation team will further refine regional marketing strategy if necessary.

3.3.1 Pitch

Exploitation team is working on a presentation which will be used as the main tool to primary attract potential customers and secondly potential partners. It will be built to reflect APOLLO's commercial branding and will make use of sales techniques, presenting APOLLO's value proposition and the benefits for its audiences. The concept is to present in a simple way farmer's challenges and how APOLLO will help them tackle them, resulting in saving time and money. If necessary, the pitch will be updated as more insights from the pilots are assessed through time and/or will be adjusted for sub target groups.

3.3.2 Brochure, leaflet and factsheets

The APOLLO project produced a brochure (M12), a leaflet (M12) to promote the services.

APOLLO
Bringing the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers
<http://apollo-h2020.eu/>

APOLLO is an EU-funded innovation project a market-ready platform of agricultural services, primarily, but not exclusively, at smallholder level.

The APOLLO project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers in Europe through the development of a market-ready platform of agricultural services, primarily, but not exclusively, at smallholder level.

These services will help farmers to make better use of their land, improve their crop yields and reduce their costs. The platform will also help farmers to improve their environmental sustainability.

APOLLO is a market-ready platform of agricultural services, primarily, but not exclusively, at smallholder level. It is designed to be accessible and easy to use by agricultural smallholder farmers, associations and agricultural consultants.

APOLLO's four services support best and optimized use of agricultural land and increasing yields.

- ILLUSTRATION: WEEDS** - What and where is best to kill?
 - APOLLO's Weed Service uses satellite imagery and machine learning to identify weeds in a field. It then provides farmers with a map showing the location and type of weeds. This information can be used to plan and execute weed control strategies more effectively.
- ILLUSTRATION: IRRIGATION** - What is the water condition of my crop?
 - APOLLO's Irrigation Service uses satellite imagery and machine learning to monitor soil moisture levels in a field. It then provides farmers with a map showing the location and type of areas that need irrigation. This information can be used to plan and execute irrigation strategies more effectively.
- ILLUSTRATION: CROP GROWTH MONITORING** - What is the current condition of my crop?
 - APOLLO's Crop Growth Monitoring Service uses satellite imagery and machine learning to monitor crop growth and health in a field. It then provides farmers with a map showing the location and type of areas that need attention. This information can be used to plan and execute crop management strategies more effectively.
- ILLUSTRATION: CROP YIELD ESTIMATION** - How much is my crop worth?
 - APOLLO's Crop Yield Estimation Service uses satellite imagery and machine learning to estimate crop yields in a field. It then provides farmers with a map showing the location and type of areas that need attention. This information can be used to plan and execute crop management strategies more effectively.

APOLLO's four services support best and optimized use of agricultural land and increasing yields.

PILOTS

HOW TO GET INVOLVED

LA MANCHA ORIENTAL, SPAIN
The APOLLO project is currently being implemented in La Mancha Oriental, Spain. The project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers in the region. The project is currently in the pilot phase and is open to smallholder farmers, associations and agricultural consultants.

APOLLO services will be piloted during the project in three countries of continental Europe: France, Serbia and Spain. The pilots will provide an opportunity for farmers to contribute to the creation of the services and their validation.

FRANCE
The APOLLO project is currently being implemented in France. The project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers in the region. The project is currently in the pilot phase and is open to smallholder farmers, associations and agricultural consultants.

SERBIA
The APOLLO project is currently being implemented in Serbia. The project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers in the region. The project is currently in the pilot phase and is open to smallholder farmers, associations and agricultural consultants.

SMALL FARMERS
The APOLLO project is currently being implemented in smallholder farms. The project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers in the region. The project is currently in the pilot phase and is open to smallholder farmers, associations and agricultural consultants.

AGRICULTURAL COOPERATIVES
The APOLLO project is currently being implemented in agricultural cooperatives. The project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers in the region. The project is currently in the pilot phase and is open to smallholder farmers, associations and agricultural consultants.

AGRICULTURAL CONSULTANTS
The APOLLO project is currently being implemented in agricultural consultants. The project aims to bring the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers in the region. The project is currently in the pilot phase and is open to smallholder farmers, associations and agricultural consultants.

HOW TO GET INVOLVED

JOIN UP TO BECOME A TRIAL USER
APOLLO will provide services to the pilot farmers in the pilot phase. The pilot farmers will be invited to join the project and become trial users. The pilot farmers will be invited to join the project and become trial users.

CONTACT US
For more information, please contact us at apollo@apollo-h2020.eu or <http://apollo-h2020.eu/>.

APOLLO
Bringing the benefits of precision agriculture to smallholder farmers

DRAXIS
Draxis is a leading provider of precision agriculture solutions. Draxis is a leading provider of precision agriculture solutions.

Figure 2: APOLLO Brochure.

Figure 3: APOLLO Brochure.

These printed documents have slightly different purposes and target audiences (see Table 10). They are distributed at a number of internal and external events, as well as on an ad-hoc basis by the project partners within the pilot regions.

Updated (and final) versions of this material are expected to be available in the next months. The material will be updated in order to reflect the commercial product and include the updated branding. The factsheets will be also available during this period.

3.3.3 Social media

The APOLLO project has established and maintains a social media presence using the services that proved to be most impactful for the primary audiences identified, as assessed from D7.8 *Dissemination Report II*.

- **Facebook:** APOLLO has established a Facebook page for the purpose of reaching out to groups and networks (such as Agri.EU - The Social Network of European Farmers³) and for engaging in public conversations with technologically-aware farmers. Facebook will be used to retain interest and boost the promotional campaign. This channel aims mostly to reach traditional farmers, cooperatives, consultants, the media and other agriculture stakeholders.
- **Twitter:** APOLLO has established a Twitter presence for amplifying the propagation of news, announcements and publications. Media, agriculture stakeholders and tech savvy farming professionals are mostly targeted through this channel.

3.3.4 Newsletter

The aim of the newsletter so far was to gain and maintain interest in the APOLLO services and act as a platform for major announcements. By entering APOLLO's preliminary commercial phase, the Newsletter has started being a channel to promote the APOLLO services and engage subscribers to inform subscribers of upcoming events, project milestones, and relevant news stories linked to the broader precision agriculture and smart farming ecosystem.

The newsletter design will be updated to fit the new commercial branding of the project but continue to be delivered using the online service MailChimp⁴. A list of subscribers will be generated by emailing a selection of contacts using the APOLLO communication database (Section 4.1), inviting subscription to the newsletter (preferably with one click).

Once entering the marketing phase project partners are expected to increase efforts to distribute the newsletter to their own networks and publicise its availability on their own channels.

3.3.5 Press kit

The APOLLO project developed a press kit for circulation to journalists (M6). The kit contains press releases, background information and contact points for interviews in each pilot country. The Press kit is made available on line through APOLLO's website. An updated press kit will be made available through APOLLO's online channels upon the implementation of APOLLO's commercial mini site and the announcement of the new services. The team is planning to also send the kit to a number of specialised media channels (e.g. agriFuture, ENRD magazine) based on the master list of communication contacts which was defined during this period (as discussed in *D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I, Section 4.1*).

3.4 Branding

Since the proposal phase, the APOLLO consortium has intended to adopt a more commercial name before entering the market. To this end, APOLLO has built an integrated and coherent visual identity aiming to form the basis for a strong commercial brand as established in M1 and 2 of the project (and extensively described in the first document of this series "*D7.1 Dissemination, Communication and Marketing Plan I*") the project's visual identity consisted of the logo, colour pallet, and additional visual elements which work together to form a coherent and recognisable whole (e.g. service icons).

To find the most suitable name to commercialise its services, the APOLLO team took under consideration APOLLO's overall value proposition for all users along with its features. It has been assessed that the commercial name needed to be based in the following elements:

³ <https://www.facebook.com/Agri.eu/>.

⁴ <http://mailchimp.com/>

- Easy to say and to remember in all languages
- Marketable
- Preferably exploit APOLLO's well established visual identity and current "branding"

Taking into account all the above, WP7 team along with the coordinators has made a list of potential options. After two successive open polls and an open vote process in the last progress meeting, and iterations between the exploitation team and coordinators the consortium has concluded to the name: "Farmore". The figure below presents all the elements Farmore demonstrates making it the best choice for APOLLO's commercialisation.

Figure 4: APOLLO's commercial name.

APOLLO is transformed into FARMORE by keeping the elements of the visual identity the same. This consists the updated name brand for APOLLO.

Figure 5: APOLLO's commercial logo.

3.5 Networks and Multipliers

The strategic use of networks and other communication multipliers is considered essential to the success of the APOLLO communications, dissemination and marketing effort. Key targets in this context include the following bodies and entities:

- COPA (Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations⁵);
- COGECA (General Committee for Agricultural Cooperation in the European Union⁶);
- ENRD (European Network for Regional Development), which as a priority thematic area on “Smart and Competitive Rural Areas”⁷);
- Eurisy (a non-profit with the stated mission of bridging space and society⁸);
- NEREUS⁹;
- EUROGI¹⁰.

A list of networks and multipliers is included in the master database of APOLLO contacts, and is continually enriched throughout the course of the project.

As the project has entered its commercial phase, these networks will be targeted with strategic communications such as press releases, major project announcements and event notifications. In addition, the events and activities organised by these organisations can be used to promote the APOLLO services.

4 Communication

Communication refers to the activities through which the project will present itself outside its own community to a wide variety of stakeholder groups.	
Target audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local and regional authorities • Academia • EU stakeholders • General public • Media • Farmers, farmer consultants and farmer cooperatives
Messages/Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote APOLLO’s scientific excellence • APOLLO helps adopt sustainable agriculture practices • Maximise the effect of direct interaction with relevant stakeholders • Present the APOLLO solution as part of the programme of speakers • Distribute APOLLO marketing material to attendees
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brochure and leaflet • Website • Social media • Events • Conferences • Press kit

⁵ <http://www.copa-cogeca.eu/CopaHistory.aspx>

⁶ <http://www.copa-cogeca.eu/CogecaHistory.aspx>

⁷ http://enrd.ec.europa.eu/themes/smart-and-competitive-rural-areas_en

⁸ <http://www.eurisy.org/>

⁹ <http://www.nereus-regions.eu/>

¹⁰ <http://www.eurogi.org/>

Partners involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate market demand for the services developed • Engage potential customers to contact with APOLLO • Seek potential partnerships among the agriculture community APOLLO's technological advancements among the scientific community • Attract interested parties to meet with APOLLO scientific experts • Establish networks and foster potential partnerships • Scientific proof of APOLLO's benefits can enhance building brand confidence to potential users • APOLLO exploitation team has drafted a list with relevant projects and initiatives, commercial solutions that can be complementary to AOLLLO, and can consist potential partners. The list is for internal use and is a living document.

A strategic campaign of event and conference attendance is planned for the lifetime of the APOLLO project. An updated list of events and conferences with respect to D7.1 is presented herein:

- **Geospatial World Forum;**
- **European Space Solutions;**
- **One or more of EURISY's** (non-profit association bridging space and society) thematic conferences (such as the 2015 precision agriculture conference¹¹);
- **One or more of EUROGI's** (European Umbrella Organisation for Geographic Information) "Imagine" conferences;
- **One or more of NEREUS'** (Network of European Regions Using Space Technologies) regional conferences;
- **INSPIRE** conference.
- **EARSC** conference for users
- **EC Workshops for Agriculture**

This list is being continuously enhanced, and an internal calendar of planned conference attendance produced with the input from project partners. APOLLO has already been represented in several events which are reported in *D7.7/8*. Although attendance to more commercial events has already started, increased participation in commercially-oriented events is planned within 2018-2019.

5 Marketing

To maximise chances of successful penetration APOLLO has drafted, early since the first stages of the project, a marketing plan with sufficient longevity to support it in its fully commercial phase. Based on the work done so far presented in documents *D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I* (M3) and *D7.10 Business Plan I* (M16), this section presents an updated version of the APOLLO Marketing Strategy. It should be noted here that the concept of marketing is inherent in all the dissemination and communication activities realised for APOLLO thus far and will continue to be so. The process of marketing the APOLLO services has already begun based on the draft strategy document presented in *D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I* and *D7.10 Business Plan I*. Pilot results will also play an important role in marketing strategy as they could indicate APOLLO's strong selling points. The first pilot results are expected in M28. Once APOLLO

¹¹ http://www.eurisy.org/event-precision-agriculture-the-added-value-of-geoinformation-and-lbs_32/about

services are finalised and a close-to-final business plan has been agreed upon, the different marketing aspects will take their final form and specific strategies based on this document will be followed. Respecting business plan confidentiality issues and the timeframe of these activities, the detailed strategies will be presented in the finalised Business Plan II (M34).

The sections below present the four Ps of marketing (namely: product, positioning, price and promotion) and the marketing methodology deployed to fit APOLLO's commercial objectives as identified to date.

5.1 The 4Ps of marketing for APOLLO

5.1.1 Product

APOLLO will provide advisory services to support farmers at all stages of the growing cycle. The initial four services will help in: i) tillage, ii) irrigation, iii) crop growth monitoring and iv) crop yield estimation. During the last months, two more services have been developed: v) weather forecast and iv) management zoning. Currently only the weather forecast is fully integrated in the APOLLO platform, while the management zoning is expected to be included in the next few months.

The table below (Table 7) summarises all six services and their descriptions.

<p>Tillage Scheduling</p>	<p>The APOLLO Tillage Scheduling service provides information on when soil tillage should be performed, according to the soil's water content. The farmer can estimate if it is possible to apply soil tillage and to identify spots where the soil cannot be treated at subparcel level (e.g. mudding spots). The service aims to help farmers achieve optimum soil workability and sustain it.</p>
<p>Irrigation Scheduling</p>	<p>The APOLLO Irrigation Scheduling service determines the correct frequency and duration of watering for avoiding problems caused to crops by over- and/or under- application of water. Users will be supported to have the optimum water usage according to plant needs.</p>
<p>Crop Growth Monitoring</p>	<p>The APOLLO Crop Growth Monitoring service will enable farmers to keep an eye on their crops' status from emergence through to harvest and provide early alerts in case of infestations and nutrient deficiencies. The service aims at optimum evaluation of crop adaptability, early identification of problems and determination of VAR zones.</p>
<p>Crop Yield Estimation</p>	<p>The APOLLO Crop Yield Estimation service forecasts crop yield before harvest, allowing an assessment of the farmer's expected income, as well as enabling the adaptability of crops and/or varieties to be evaluated in combination with Crop Growth Monitoring service. The service aims at optimum analysis and comparison of field productivity and effective transfer to industry (market vs storage).</p>
<p>Weather Forecast</p>	<p>The APOLLO Weather Forecast service forecasts weather at highly localised level and allows farmers to improve management of labour as well as to improve their timing of operations. The service provides field-level data on surface weather parameters such as Temperature, Humidity and Vector Wind at 2m high, Precipitation etc., and agrometeorological parameters such as FAO56 PM Reference</p>

	Evapotranspiration and leaf wetness duration. Also, it provides alerts and notifications to the users regarding high impact weather events such as hail storms, frost, heat waves, blizzards, lightning and gales. The weather forecast service offers precipitation and temperature predictions for seven upcoming days.
<p style="text-align: center;">Farm Management Zoning</p>	The APOLLO Farm Management Zoning identifies crop performance pattern within a field that repeats across seasons by analysing historical data of vegetation indices. According these crop patterns, farmers can adjust their management practices (e.g. higher fertilisation in deficient pockets) and management tasks (e.g. better estimation of when grapes will ripen within the field) within her/his fields with the goal to achieve higher yields and yields of higher quality.

Table 7: APOLLO services description.

The services are described in technical detail in *D4.1 A suite of agricultural services* (confidential document).

5.1.2 APOLLO positioning

Zooming in from the broad picture of the market and its evolution drawn before, it is important to understand how APOLLO positions itself vis-à-vis competition across the different services it provides.

5.1.2.1 Tillage Scheduling Services

Tillage scheduling is of great importance for farmers because poor timing may destroy soil's texture^{12,13,14}. The competitive landscape analysis confirms that there is virtually no commercially or even project-based available solution for tillage scheduling. **APOLLO's tillage scheduling service will address this problem by providing information on soil's workability level** through an algorithm that integrates soil moisture data (that are derived from Sentinel-1) and soil data (that are derived from harmonised world soil database¹⁵).

5.1.2.2 Irrigation Scheduling Services

As water resources become scarcer, the need for efficient water management becomes imperative. This need will be even more evident in the cases of countries currently planning to impose costs on water consumption by farmers. In Greece, for example, it is expected that in a few years from now farmers will be required to pay for the water they use. In such cases, this will become the greatest cost in the agricultural practice, making efficient water management extremely important. As analysed in *D7.10 Business Plan I*, the irrigation service represents a potentially unparalleled service on the market – low-cost and timely remote sensing of field soil moisture. As such, it represents a large technical advance beyond current technical capacities. There is definite scope for the integration of in-situ data to improve technical added-value of the solution. Highly-accurate point data

¹² Karlen, D.L., Wollenhaupt, N.C., Erbach, D.C., Berry, E.C., Swan, J.B., Eash, N.S., and Jordahl, J.L. 1994. Long-ter tillage effects on soil quality. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 32(4):313-327.

¹³ Mosaddeghi, M.R., Hajabbasi, M.A., Hemmat, A., and Afyuni, M. 2000. Soil compactibility as affected by soil moisture content and farmyard manure in central Iran. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 55:87-97.

¹⁴ Willekens, K., Vandecasteele, B., Buchan, D., and De Neve, S. 2014. Soil quality is positively affected by reduced tillage and compost in an intensive vegetable cropping system. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 82:61-71.

¹⁵ <http://www.fao.org/soils-portal/soil-survey/soil-maps-and-databases/harmonized-world-soil-database-v12/en/>

from soil sensors and detailed soil surveys (i.e. sampling soil across intervals in a grid) can significantly improve accuracy of the APOLLO irrigation scheduling service. In such a scheme, this APOLLO service will allow for cost-effective monitoring of irrigation in a good spatial and temporal resolution, allowing for quick reactions to plant water needs and pipe leakages. This will be especially of use in large and remote fields. As Sentinel-1 is expected to provide high resolution soil moisture data^{16,17}, and SAR sensors are not dependent on weather conditions as optical sensors are for providing irrigation advice, APOLLO will provide more accurate and frequent irrigation advice compared to the existing products that are based on optical and simulated data. It is worth mentioning most of the currently existing solutions rely primarily (if not solely) on the installation of in-situ sensors.

5.1.2.3 Crop Growth Monitoring

As identified in D7.5 Market Analysis, crop monitoring services are amongst the most common in the competitive landscape. Against this backdrop, APOLLO's crop growth monitoring service will include crop status, estimation of LAI (Leaf Area Index) and estimation of biomass. This service will provide more accurate and frequent data than the existing services, due to the fact that Sentinel-2 optical is of high accuracy with more frequent revisit times and has high correlation of its vegetation indices with the actual site measurements such as vigour, biomass and LAI^{18,19}. In addition, APOLLO's crop growth monitoring service will provide the capability to farmers and agricultural consultants to manage their data for their own purposes such as producing prescription maps for variable rate fertilization and pesticide application along with temporal and spatial statistics related to crop parameters measurements

5.1.2.4 Yield Estimation

As with crop monitoring, yield estimation services are relatively widespread. APOLLO's yield estimation service will provide information to farmers on secondary products (e.g. straw) in addition to main product yield estimation. Pre-harvest estimates using satellite or drone imagery provide a more accurate estimate, due to higher spatial resolution of the data. However, they are point values (in time), and they are not updated as harvest approaches, as is the case with the APOLLO service. This service offers a more precise figure and the opportunity to make better logistical and commercial arrangements using this information. Both of these issues affect farmer income: smooth and timely completion of post-harvest operations minimises losses and avoids extra costs from having hired too many people/trucks, or last-minute arrangements from not having hired enough.

5.1.2.5 Weather Forecast

APOLLO Weather Forecast is a highly localised weather forecast service, offering more relevant data than currently available alternatives, allows farmers to improve management of labour as well as to improve their timing of operations. The service relies on the use of high resolution numerical

¹⁶ Gruber, A., Wagner, W., Hegyiova, A., Greifeder, F., and Schläffer, S. 2013. Potential of Sentinel-1 for high-resolution soil moisture monitoring. *IGARSS 2013*:4030-4033.

¹⁷ Paloscia, S., Pettinato, S., Santi, E., Notarnicola, C., Pasolli, L., and Repucci, A. 2013. Soil moisture mapping using Sentinel-1 images: Algorithm and preliminary validation. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 134:234-248.

¹⁸ Clevers, J.G.P.W., and Gitelson, A.A. 2013. Remote estimation of crop and grass chlorophyll and nitrogen content using red-edge bands on Sentinel-2 and -3. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 23:344-351.

¹⁹ Frampton, W.J., Dash, J., Watmough, G., and Milton, E.J. 2013. Evaluating the capabilities of Sentinel-2 for quantitative estimation of biophysical variables in vegetation. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 82:83-92.

weather and atmospheric data assimilation systems, along with machine learning based model output statistics to improve the produced weather forecasts. APOLLO provides the service horizontally along with each other APOLLO service. This allows farmers to have highly localised information for all conditions helping them to take decisions.

5.1.2.6 Farm Management Zoning

Farm Management Zoning identifies crop performance pattern within a field that repeats across seasons by analysing historical data of vegetation indices. According these crop patterns, farmers can adjust their management practices with the goal to achieve higher yields and yields of higher quality. Management zones are presented to users of this service through the web map visualisation component, appearing as a separate layer of polygons over the satellite base layer. As a result, the farmer can adjust treatments (e.g. higher fertilisation in deficient pockets) and management tasks (e.g. better estimation of when grapes will ripen within the field) within her/his fields to improve yield quantity and quality, and hence to maximise income.

5.1.3 Price

Pricing schemes considered as options for APOLLO were extensively analysed in the previous deliverable *D7.10 Business Plan I*. By the time *D7.10* was published, the two new APOLLO services (i.e. Weather Forecast and Farm Management Zoning) were at early stages of development therefore no specific pricing schemes were analysed for these services. However, APOLLO's pricing scheme will not change due to the introduction of the new services. At this point it is necessary to recall that Weather Forecast service is a service provided horizontally – along with all APOLLO services and the current thinking is that it will not be charged for, as a separate service. On the other hand, APOLLO Farm Management Zoning constitutes a separate service and as such it will be considered to be sold separately following the same principles of assessing a pricing scheme with the other four services presented in *D7.10 Business Plan I*. This new service has not yet been fully integrated in the APOLLO platform and therefore a solid analysis on potential pricing is not yet feasible. However, some first option is being considered towards following an annual fee pricing model for these two services.

Overall, pricing of the first four APOLLO services is still under finalisation as the services are being fine-tuned and first evaluation results are expected in the following months. Analysis on selected pricing schemes is expected to be presented in the final business plan deliverable *D7.11 Business Plan II*.

5.1.4 Promotion

APOLLO's promotion will follow a marketing process analysed in Section 5.2. The overall concept is to go along with the technical advancements of the services in order to successfully initiate their commercialisation. To this end, three broad phases underpinning the APOLLO marketing process can be visualised as shown in the following flowchart:

Figure 6: APOLLO's marketing phases.

During the first period of the project (approximately until M12), APOLLO developed and shaped its services and the platform through which they will be made available. During that period (approximately one year), promotion aimed primarily in disseminating the APOLLO idea in the agricultural community (including farmers, consultants, cooperatives, retailers, etc). The aim was to start developing a solid network of interested stakeholders, potential users or/and potential partners. This phase continues in order to ensure smoothly transit from the project phase to product phase.

Currently APOLLO is in the preliminary marketing phase. This phase prepares the ground for phase three. Upon the finalisation of the services and the platform, promotion will enter the second phase. the full-scale campaign, that will follow once the first results from the pilots will be assessed from a marketing perspective This second phase aims at a genuine marketing phase. The goal is to develop and release strong campaigns promoting the commercial product. Being highly dependent on business aspects such as concrete value proposition, pricing scheme, etc. the APOLLO team has developed a promotional strategy in line with the business plan so far, and APOLLO's potential based on pilot users' feedback. Marketing process outlines the detailed activities which will be implemented It is a living activity which is adjusted and fine-tuned with the progress of the project and the business plan.

According to the latest assessments, key differentiators for APOLLO are identified to be the following:

- High temporal resolution
- Easy to interpret and use information
- Farm-specific (highly localised) meteorological data which accompany horizontally all APOLLO services
- Information is available to all through the APOLLO services.
- Copernicus data enhances cost-competitiveness

Promotion uses the set of channels, tools and activities described in chapters 3-5 to get APOLLO's commercial messages across the different target audiences.

Branding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New logo • Colour pallet • Icons • Any additional visual elements
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Blog (i.e. articles production) • Social media • Newsletters • Direct outreach through pilot activities
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation • Pitch • Brochure • Leaflet • Factsheets • Press kit

Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Media coverage (i.e TV and radio presence) • Open regional information days for farmers, farmer consultants and cooperatives • Third party conferences/workshops/events • Organise conferences/workshops/events • Scientific publications
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Table 8: Promotional material.

The table below (Table 9) is drawn from D7.1 and gives an updated summary of the tools at the disposal of the project, describes their purpose and indicates to which of the target audiences the tools are primarily aimed (main targets in bold), and which level of activity the tool is designed to achieve.

Communication Tool	Target						Purpose	Activity
	Farmers and Associations	Agronomists	Policy/LRA *	Research	Media	Public		
Website	x	x	x	x	x	x	Raising awareness of the project's goals, activities and results and promoting the APOLLO platform to the main target audience: farmers, farmers' associations and agricultural consultants	ENGAGE
Newsletter	x	x	x		x	x	A regular electronic newsletter will be used for announcing project-related events, communicating project news, maintaining the interest and awareness of subscribers as the project progresses.	ENGAGE
Brochure	x			x		x	Providing a detailed overview of the benefits and advantages of the APOLLO service with a view to creating brand awareness and attracting new customers.	ENLIGHT
Leaflet	x	x	x			x	Attracting the attention of target audiences with a small number of key messages, triggering brand awareness and encouraging visitors to the website	INFORM
Factsheets	x	x	x				Summarising facts on the six services offered by APOLLO	ENLIGHT
Social Media	x	x			x	x	Creating dialogue with vocal target groups, establish a community of "followers", announce events, post news, and draw additional visitors to the website	ENGAGE
Press Kit					x	x	Facilitating the publication in the media of articles or stories about the APOLLO project	ENGAGE
Presentation	x	x	x	x			Attract the attention of potential target groups encouraging them to get involved in APOLLO, enhance brand awareness and encourage partnerships	ENGAGE
Pitch	x	x					Genuine commercial presentation to attract customers	ENGAGE

User Requirements Survey	x					Whilst not <i>per se</i> a communication tool, the user requirements survey will be used for the dual purpose of collecting valuable information about consumer preferences whilst also highlighting the features of the six APOLLO services.	ENGAGE
Event information package	x	x				Targeted collection of materials aimed at collecting the key material required for maximising the impact of face-to-face interaction	ENGAGE

Table 9: Communication tools and audiences (main tools in bold).

5.2 Marketing process

Overall, the APOLLO marketing strategy makes use of a combination of tools and activities that have begun from the inauguration of the project and will continue until M34 (end of the project). Additionally to the findings of the previous sections of this document, the marketing strategy takes input²⁰ from previous work, which is referenced in the following documents, namely: D7.1 “Communication, Marketing and Dissemination” (M3), D7.5 “Market Analysis Report” (M5), D7.7 “Communication and Dissemination Report” (M6, M18), D7.10 Business Plan I (M16). Figure 7 shows the marketing strategy process. The main “ingredients” presented will emerge from the key pillars of the marketing strategy and the development of the business plan. The outputs of these activities will in turn act as input for the marketing plan.

Figure 7. Marketing strategy process and main “ingredients”.

Since M18 when the first draft of the Business Plan became available the following assessments have been made for each of the input nodes (marketing “ingredients”):

²⁰ All referenced documents are vital for shaping the Marketing strategy therefore they consist in living documents. They are updated regularly by the consortium. All critical updates will be reflected in their upcoming final versions.

- **Unique selling point:** APOLLO provides modular, easy to use, affordable to all services through a dedicated platform. Services provide accurate information to help users tackle and plan the basic farm operations. APOLLO's uniqueness is expected to be finalised taking inputs from the analysis of the first results from the pilots and the refinement of the business plan.
- **User feedback:** APOLLO has collected the first feedback from its alpha users, which is reported in *D6.5 1st Intermediate Evaluation Report*. Based on the findings, all APOLLO services, as well as the APOLLO platform presented high acceptance, reliability, good usability experience and degree of satisfaction. Most of the services were considered by users easy/very easy to understand, while in terms of accuracy the farmers found every service accurate (except yield estimation, because there were not enough data). Fothcoming activities under WP6 will provide further insights on these features with the progress of the project.

Crop consultants were found to be mostly in favour with irrigation scheduling and crop growth monitoring as they found it more useful for their agronomic advices to the farmers. In addition, consultants found accurate yield estimation and crop growth monitoring services.

Both farmers and crop consultants found the APOLLO platform to have a very satisfactory quality, by providing an overall good value for their needs. In addition, both of the user groups believed that the platform is not difficult to be learned and that is providing better results than other platforms. This makes users believe that they would probably recommend the final platform to friends and/or colleagues.

- **Market and competition analysis:** Latest analysis was reported in *D7.10 Business Plan I*, although it is a living process. To ensure concreteness and sustainability, marketing strategy is based on the latest analysis and refinements are being considered only if major changes will occur.
- **Business plan development:** Latest business plan development is reported in *D7.10 Business Plan I*. Further considerations are under development and will be finalised during the next months of the project.
- **Commercial name and commercial mini site:** APOLLO has proceeded to selecting a commercial name which is demonstrated in section 4.5. A commercial mini site is planned to be available on line once the commercial name logo is finalised. A sneak peak of the mini site is shown in the following figure.

Figure 8: A first mock-up draft of APOLLO's commercial mini site.

Commercial mini site will introduce APOLLO's commercial identity, present APOLLO as a product and overall it will complete APOLLO's preliminary commercial phase. It is expected to attract more potential customers and interested parties seeking partnerships.

Elements of the APOLLO marketing strategy is introduced in terms of the activities undertaken in each of the marketing phases.

5.2.1 Phase 1: Promoting the APOLLO idea

Target groups: All

Description: The first phase, which started at the beginning of the project, concerned the establishment of a brand identity and a core audience of potentially interested users to whom the idea of the APOLLO services was promoted.

Activities: Communication activities played a key role in this preliminary phase.

- Event attendance and regional info days organised by pilot partners
- Media presence
- Designing and developing the APOLLO logo
- Designing and implementing the APOLLO project website
- Publication of the APOLLO brochure, leaflet and fact sheets
- Promotion of the project on social media

Impact: This phase was the corner stone on which APOLLO has built its brand identity for the commercial phase. According to *D7.8 Dissemination Report II*, APOLLO's presence on the media

(TV, radio and press) through consortium representatives in the pilot countries but also abroad (i.e. APOLLO's coordinator presence in the Italian TV) has proved to be very successful. More than a dozen farmers and agricultural consultants in the pilots were interested to get involved in APOLLO and requested more information from local representatives. APOLLO also gained more than fifteen new Newsletter and trial user subscribers. In addition, representatives of relevant projects and individuals from various countries such as Sweden, Italia and Serbia, contacted the APOLLO team seeking ways of potential collaboration.

Status: Promoting the APOLLO idea is has given its place to a marketing focused methodology (i.e phase 2 and phase 3 described in the following sections).

5.2.2 Phase 2: Preliminary marketing

Target groups: All

Description: This phase is the bridge between phase 1: promoting the APOLLO idea and phase 3: strong marketing campaign. To maximise chances of a successful strong marketing campaign, two streams of activities were identified.

Activities:

- **Execution of primary market research on APOLLO target customers.** This is necessary in order to base key marketing decisions on solid data (e.g. deciding on the use of a promotion channel such as radio);
- **Transition from project-based to product-based promotional activities.** First mentioned in *D7.2 Communication, Dissemination and Marketing Plan II*, these activities include the selection of a commercial name, the creation of a product-focused mini-site, and the continued advancement of the public perception of APOLLO as a viable commercial entity, as opposed to a temporary research action.

5.2.2.1 Market research

Preliminary market research is a basic input for developing a successful marketing plan. It involves several actions providing valuable insights on APOLLO's target audiences and assessing the impact of communication tools used. Drawing input from the series of documents *D7.7/7.8 Dissemination Report I/II* the following impact for each identified activity is reported as follows. Furthermore, the future use of each activity is presented.

1. Evaluation of effectiveness of tools e.g. newsletter, website.

The effectiveness of the tools used to communicate APOLLO messages with potential customers and users is being regularly evaluated. The impact of the communication tools and methods is assessed along with the progress of the project.

Impact:

- **Traditional media** mostly TV and radio and secondly newspapers, were proven to be highly effective channels to attract new customers/users. TV and radio appearance has reportedly (see section 5.1, Impact) stimulated several new interested agricultural professionals to contact the local partners asking how they could be involved in APOLLO, and/or subscribe as trial users through the portal. Traditional media appearance had so far, the greatest impact in Serbia.

Until today, it has been shown that farmers are greatly influenced and engaged by their colleagues in the region and through APOLLO presence in the media, mostly TV and radio. The APOLLO team is exploiting these current conclusions by continuing its strong presence in the media and by being approachable to all interested parties.

Thus far, the APOLLO team involved in pilot activities has observed that the interpersonal approach through the co-creation process is the most powerful communication and marketing tool towards attracting potential customers. Another strong communication tool proved so far to have brought many new users wanting to get involved is the call to action sections integrated in APOLLO's website.

Follow up activities: APOLLO representatives will seek to enhance APOLLO promotion through traditional channels. In addition, advertisement in trade journals will also be investigated through the local partners. Local partners will provide relevant feedback, including recommendations on what are the farmers used to read.

- **Website (APOLLO project)** aimed to serve as the online marketing tool of the project. *D7.8 Dissemination Report II* has shown that the website was visited almost half-half by new and returning users. The website seems to be the tool for the audiences to get more details on the project after being attracted by all other means. The website's impact is expected to change drastically upon the implementation of the commercial mini site (see section 7.2.).

Follow up activities: APOLLO will introduce the commercial mini site.

- **Social media** facilitated APOLLO to establish a solid network of contacts and "followers". Supported by and supporting all partner activities, social media are considered to be a high impact tool.

Follow up activities: Social media campaigns focused on specific audiences will be launched in the following months.

- **Newsletter** Although subscribers' rate is increasing through time it seems that the Newsletter might not be the major tool to promote APOLLO services to new audience. However, it is a great tool to promote APOLLO to its existing community and retain their interest while engage them as we enter the commercial phase to get more involved in APOLLO and retain them as a pool of early adopters and potential customers.

Follow up activities: The Newsletter will continue to focus on how farmers, consultants and cooperatives can improve their farming practices and how APOLLO can help them achieve it. It will remain the primary tool to inform all target groups about the latest APOLLO advancements and targeted events.

- **Dissemination material** (e.g. **brochure** and **leaflet**) approximately 200 copies were distributed to farmers, consultants and cooperatives, mostly in agricultural events. Actual impact of this tool is trivial to assess but it is considered to have been of medium impact compared to traditional media which is considered to be of high impact. Dissemination material will attract website visitors, engage trial user and newsletter subscription rates, increase new followers and retain interest.

Follow up activities: All dissemination material is being updated to reflect APOLLO's commercial brand and will include the new services and platform screenshots. The updated brochure and leaflet will aim primarily to potential customers and users and secondly in stakeholders. Regional teams will be the main points of distribution in pilot countries during co creation meetings, info days etc. and in events across Europe and beyond.

- **Events and conferences (both organised by third parties and APOLLO consortium)** helped APOLLO built a network across the smart farming community, get insights on relevant initiatives and approach potential customers.

Follow up activities: The target is to increase participation in trade shows and fairs promoting from now on APOLLO as a commercial product.

2. Consolidate lessons learned from the pilots.

The three APOLLO pilot sites in Greece, Serbia and Spain serve as the entry points into establishing a foothold in markets in those countries, and from this starting point, the user base is grown systematically, year on year. As the pilot countries will be the main entry points of APOLLO commercial product, understanding the tools and methodologies that proved to work best or worst in any case is vital. Although the main target audiences are the same for all pilot countries, regional specificities should not be ignored. This will enable the identification of best practices for each country and each target group.

Impact: For each country, there seem to be different opportunities for APOLLO to enter the local market. For Greece it is the irrigated crops and the upcoming water charges, in Serbia the commercial farming sector is underserved by the agricultural technology while in Spain small farmers seem to have low adoption of digital solutions in semi-arid regions.

Follow up activities: As these were the first assessments, a more detailed analysis will follow until M27 in order to consolidate messages accordingly for each region. After M29 and the first pilot results special focus will be given for each regional strategy and specific target group.

3. Identify champions.

In each pilot country, partners involved in the piloting processes have begun to identify farmers and/or consultants that can be considered as “champions”. The concept of “champion” - as first presented in D7.1 - is that “champion” farmers and/or consultants can be engaged to contact their association, if they are a member of one, or their regional colleagues, to register their interest in the services and lobby new subscriptions acting as brokers for the APOLLO services. This is necessary in order to take into account differences between the structure of the agricultural industry between countries (e.g. working methods, the size, composition and influence of cooperatives, producers and groupings etc.).

Impact: Potential champions are being under assessment and will be identified after the first pilot results.

Follow up activities: Pilot partners are gathering feedback for this scope which will be used to identify the right champions for APOLLO as described above.

4. Finalisation of business plan: USPs, niche and customer groups.

A solid marketing plan it is essential that APOLLO's value proposition, business model and customer target groups are agreed upon.

Impact: The exploitation team works closely with the coordinator in order to finalise as soon as possible the business aspects. They will provide the main inputs for the final marketing strategy.

Follow up activities: The final business plan will be presented in the document *D7.11 Business Plan II*.

5. Investigate the possibility of a primary target customer (amongst farmers, consultants, coops.) based on experience with pilots.

Based on the experience of the pilots, were investigated if one or more groups could act as primary target customers for APOLLO.

Impact: It has been assessed that all three groups consist primary target customer for APOLLO.

Follow up activities: Key messages will be tailored accordingly for this/these region(s), boosting the potential for regional market penetration.

6. Decide on target countries and regions beyond Greece, Serbia, Spain.

Using the outcomes of the services validation and all other results regarding the customer targets, APOLLO team will seek to identify other (primarily) potential EU markets where APOLLO could have good chances of success.

Impact: As a result of the communication and promotional activities, similar initiatives and farmers from other countries have shown interest for APOLLO.

Follow up activities: The team is exploring all possible synergies and extensions based on APOLLO's features. Upon the first pilot results it is expected that

7. Analyse the potential impact of marketing tools at national/regional/local level in the target countries.

As a consequential step of identifying new potential target markets beyond the pilot countries, the related analysis and impact assessment of marketing channels will be conducted.

Impact: Most impactful tools seem to be traditional media for users and for partnerships social media, website.

Follow up activities: Market research is a living task and further assessments will be extracted by the end of this preliminary phase thus continuous analysis at national and regional level is foreseen. Additionally, first results from the pilots (expected in M28) will most likely provide amongst others valuable insights in regard to this step. Both these assessments will help to fine tune the marketing strategy per target group (as target groups are identified up to now) and/or it can lead to the introduction of different target groups as well.

5.2.2.2 Project- to product-based promotion

In the context of commercialising APOLLO, the consortium is planning to conduct a poll in order to decide APOLLO's commercial name. The name will be in line with what APOLLO offers to its users and is expected to be finalised end of M24 as described in section 4.4.

The mini-site is expected to be created until the end of M25, presenting APOLLO (under its new commercial name) services as a product. In its initial deployment, visitors will be directed via hyperlink to the APOLLO project website for further details. Following the release of the first working prototype of the APOLLO service, (as previously described in *D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan*), a complete commercial site will be made available at a different address (corresponding to the new name of the APOLLO product).

The original project site will remain accessible through a link (e.g. "powered by APOLLO"), but the focus of the commercial site will be promoting and selling the services, rather than discussing the project. The implementation will make use of the finalised commercial brand.

5.2.3 Phase 3: Full-scale campaign

Target groups: Customers, users and early adopters

Description: The aim of the third phase will be to lead APOLLO into being a commercial service in the market. It will be the natural evolution of the preliminary marketing phase. The full-scale marketing campaign will aim primarily to customers as they will be identified in the exploitation (including business plan refinement activities) and early adopters. To boost value for potential customers promotion will also target actual users. Focusing on challenges that users tackle with every day in their fields can create a demand around services that APOLLO is able to offer. APOLLO's value proposition will be used to build this strategy which will be further tailored for the pilot regions. Convincing users that APOLLO provides solutions that highly benefit their agricultural operations and save them time and money will lead to a demand in the market that APOLLO can

address. Even though farmers can also be users only and not customers, this demand will act as a leverage for other potential customers.

The campaign will include messages tailored to all identified target groups and it is expected to be based in regional specificities (e.g. environmental conditions, specific crops, current practices etc). It will also address to the general market promoting APOLLO's added value.

Activities: The figure below demonstrates the main promotional activities for an effective marketing campaign.

Figure 9: An overview of the timeline of the marketing activities and the exploitation milestones.

The APOLLO project spans two agricultural seasons, May to September 2017 and 2018. This provides a general framework for the timing of the communication, dissemination and marketing effort aimed at the eventual customers of APOLLO: (small) farmers and agricultural consultants.

The bulk of APOLLO's updated published materials (brochure, leaflet, factsheets) will be available as from M26. The communications plan above considers two periods of intensification. The publication of the commercial site and the new services and the activities which follow the first pilot results. The overview summarises the main milestones of the exploitation activities and the marketing phases.

The key activities underpinning the strong marketing campaign are the following:

1. Strong involvement of pilots.

Pilots are the primary target markets as all services are being co-created and validated in these countries. Networks, established contacts and confidence that is building up among the users and the APOLLO team will be strongly reclaimed towards developing a strong promotional campaign based on each country's needs. User requirements, user feedback from local APOLLO partners combined with the establishment of solid relations with the local/regional "champions" is crucial for APOLLO's uptake. Specific target groups

2. Increased local media presence.

Having identified that, as already mentioned above, traditional communication channels are the most effective method so far, local media presence is planned to be increased. Local APOLLO team representatives and "champion" farmers/consultants will be used to promote APOLLO's niche and results, eventually engaging new potential customers.

3. Transforming from project to a solid product.

To have a successful marketing campaign it is important to deliver the message that APOLLO is not another product coming from a project. The campaign will deliver a strong message regarding the concreteness of APOLLO's services, its added value, and deliver the product's actual impact in real conditions to the wider agricultural community.

6 Dissemination

Dissemination activities aim to inform the scientific community on scientific results arising from or based upon the activities conducted in the framework of the project. In this project dissemination is not considered to be a primary goal, as the project's aim is to support the generation of a commercial service.	
Target audiences	Scientific community
Messages/Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present APOLLO's scientific advancements and promote APOLLO's state of the art technologies
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Scientific conferences
Tools to exploit dissemination for marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website blog and Newsletter • Social media
Partners involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities and commercial SMEs
Expected Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminate APOLLO's technological advancements among the scientific community • Attract interested parties to meet with APOLLO scientific experts • Facilitate network development and foster potential partnerships • Use it as scientific proof of APOLLO's benefits. Enhance brand confidence to potential users/customers • Partnerships with similar projects can prove useful for the commercialisation of the services. Up to date information and stay at the forefront of technological advances.

6.1.1 Publication of scientific results

Academic and research partners in the consortium publish scientific papers based on the results of the research carried out within APOLLO. These papers are targeted at the following indicative list of journals:

- Remote Sensing of Environment (Elsevier);
- Precision Agriculture (Springer);
- Computers and Electronics in Agriculture (Elsevier);
- International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation (Elsevier);
- ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (Elsevier).

Regarding the scientific publications, the consortium takes in account the H2020 Open Access Policy as required by the European Commission. At the same time, the commercial nature of the project is respected and care is taken not to jeopardise the project's competitive advantages. As mentioned

above, as the project reaches its final year, efforts will be mainly focus in promoting APOLLO services and platform. However, dissemination activities facilitate building partnerships and networks. Dissemination will respect the confidentiality of intellectual property as laid out in the consortium’s IP Policy (see deliverable *D7.3*). All publications are analytically reported in the series of documents *D7.7-9 Dissemination Report I-III*.

6.1.2 Presence in scientific conferences

APOLLO targets the following scientific conferences:

- International conference on Precision Agriculture;
- European Conference on Precision Agriculture;
- IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium;
- International Conference of Agricultural Engineering;
- Remote Sensing for Agriculture, Ecosystems, and Hydrology;
- Asian Conference on Precision Agriculture – ACPA.

Extensive list of participation in scientific conferences is reported in the series of documents *D7.7-9 Dissemination Report I-III*.

7 Monitoring and Evaluation

The impact of the APOLLO communication activities is being monitored on an ongoing basis and will be reported in the relevant deliverable (Communication, Marketing and Dissemination Reports; *D7.9*; due *M34*). Data on the communication, dissemination and marketing activities of each partner is collected using an online survey tool to ensure standardisation of responses.

The table below presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which were defined in the *D7.1 Dissemination Communication and Marketing Plan I* and used to evaluate the success of the project’s actions. In each case, the data will be examined with the aim of excluding those linked to actions by members of the consortium.

Key Performance Indicators	Target value	Achieved value M(24)	Means of verification
Visitors to the APOLLO webpage	5000	2762	Analytics monitoring software (Google Analytics)
Subscribers to the newsletter	3000	97	Newsletter system dashboard (MailChimp)
"Likes" of the APOLLO page on Facebook	300	105	Page details on Facebook
Members of the APOLLO LinkedIn group	50	7	Group details on LinkedIn
Followers of the APOLLO Twitter account	50	188	Account details on Twitter
Articles or appearances in the media about the APOLLO project	45	21	Monitoring and reporting by WP7 team and project partners
Events attended by the APOLLO project team	15	22	
Printed communication material distributed	2500	200	

Table 10: Key Performance Indicators

8 Conclusion

The communication, marketing and dissemination plan of the APOLLO project is intended to be a comprehensive and living document which outlines the actions, tools and channels to be used throughout the project in the promotion of the APOLLO product. This document presented the updated version of the first document of the series (D7.1).

Having started since M17, Dissemination, Communication and Marketing activities, served in facilitating APOLLO enter into its commercial identity and find its way slowly into the market. All activities from M24 onwards, aim to promote the commercial brand of APOLLO "FARMORE". It is a vital step in order to efficiently support a business plan, maximise the probability of successful market penetration and user uptake. Communication efforts will be mainly achieved through the channels that have proven to have the strongest impact so far, such as traditional media, social media and peer to peer activities. Pilot regions (and countries) continue to be in the spotlight of these activities with the pilot partners playing a crucial role. Further promotional steps will be built in the outlined strategy presented in this document. Nevertheless, strategy is being updated as the project develops momentum, and as further insights are acquired into the target audiences and future customers of the operational services. Concrete value proposition and a clear identification of customers versus users will help shape into detail marketing campaigns.

9 References

- European Commission, 2016. Greening. http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/direct-support/greening/index_en.htm
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